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PATTERNS OF STUDENT'S CURRICULUM ENGAGEMENT IN AN ON-DEMAND ONLINE CURRICULUM

An exploratory study at Charles Sturt University

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INTRODUCTION

Charles Sturt University (CSU) Engineering is a new programme established in 2016. This programme was established from scratch in a university that had not previously taught engineering. This was taken as an opportunity to build an all-new programme structure and philosophy [1]. Students at CSU Engineering complete a sequence of three semester-long PBL-style challenges across the first three semesters; after this point, they commence work placements in industry. The underlying technical curriculum that supports the projects is broken down into fine-grained learning

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activities called 'topics' that are offered online using the Realizeit platform [2]. Each topic is intended to take a typical student around three hours to complete. Although topics are arranged into a tree structure where the recommended learning order is made explicit [3], see Figure 1, the curriculum is based on a philosophy of self-directed learning; students have a considerable amount of freedom in deciding how and when they engage with the topics in the online environment.

Figure 1: The CSU Engineering topic tree.

In this way, the students engage with theory at the point at which it is required in their work, rather than in a synchronous syllabus driven manner. This has the advantage of ensuring the content is relevant at the point at which it is learnt; however it also introduces the risk of how the students manage their progression through the tree. In this paper, we present exploratory research in which the authors attempt to understand student engagement in this online environment.

1 ORGANISATION OF THE ON-DEMAND CURRICULUM

1.1 Topic Acquisition and progression

Students are required to complete a total of at least 240 topics from the tree before they are eligible to go on industry placement in their fourth semester. While 80 of these topics are compulsory, selected after a process of engaging with industry partners [1], the students are free to choose the other 160 from throughout the tree. The topic tree consists of multiple branches comprised of sequences of topics which are strongly related and scaffolded on top of the other. Although there is no required order in which to students should complete topics, the structure of the tree provides clear guidance as to the recommended learning path. Each topic in turn consists of a number of learning activities.

Progress is first and foremost the responsibility of the students as self-directed learning is an important element of the programme. There are essentially no immediate consequences for an inadequate rate of progression through the topic tree. Where the PBL challenges have mid- and end-of-semester milestones, the topic tree has only two requirements, and neither of them manifests until the very end of the three-semester subject. Lindsay and Morgan [3] observed that this effectively leads to the emergence of two sub-cohorts – one who was up to date, and one that was well behind and unlikely to complete.

While some measures have been taken to signal adequate progression to encourage students to stay on track [4], some students still lag behind. A challenge with learning in online environments is that while all behaviour is logged, it is not straightforward to determine how this data captures effective study behaviour, and how to interpret it in the light of potential interventions.

1.2 Student behaviour and student success

Student success is among the most widely studied topics in higher education, however, little is known about effective study behaviour in online and blended environments. Carroll [5] postulated that the basis of all student success is rooted in effective study behaviour, which consists of time on task and the behaviour itself. He states that students with a great aptitude do not automatically pass their exams: even strong students have to open their books and use their time in a meaningful way to learn the materials. A weaker student can achieve the same outcomes by spending more time on the materials and/or in a more effective manner. There is never just one way of being successful as a student, according to Carroll, there are however many ways not to be successful. These two elements of effective study behaviour were taken as starting points to explore behaviours in the online environment, as they were previously used in similar settings of research [6].

1.3 Logging student behaviour in the online environment

The analysis of data that is logged in online systems with the aim of understanding and improving learning is often referred to as learning analytics. This has been a trending topic for the past years, but understanding the data that is logged and interpreting it, is more complicated than it may seem. The data that is logged by the Realizeit system includes all timestamped attempts at the topics in the tree, as well as detailed metrics capturing what happens within these attempts, and the context within which the attempt was made. Through this data, it becomes clear how students navigate their way through the topic tree, how much they do in a set period of time,

etc. It is up to the researchers and teachers to try to understand what kind of behaviours this data reflects and what that means for learning.

Van den Bogaard and De Vries [7] showed that by just using data mining techniques, or even AI, we can predict success easily, but we often end up with predictor variables and algorithms that are almost impossible to conceptualise and use as a starting point for meaningful interventions. Additionally, the data shows only what happens within the platform, but can't log data on what happens on other screens. While working on a topic, a student may be doing something else on a different screen on their computers, or they leave a topic open while they take a break. The data continues to get logged, but it is not clear what it represents. Actual time on task is therefore difficult to calculate. Research at the University of Central Florida [8] examined metrics from the Realizeit learning platform and found that differences in student performance are an effective predictor for who will succeed and who will not. However, the use of the platform in this study does not reflect the unique manner in which it is being used at Charles Sturt University. The challenge for the teachers at CSU Engineering is to develop metrics of behaviour that support understanding effective study behaviour in this unique curriculum.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Research questions

As there are many different ways of looking at behaviour and defining it, we took the topic tree as our starting point. The tree is the main structure of the online environment, so this seems like an obvious starting point. The research question for this study is:

How do the students move through the topic tree in terms of actual behaviour and time spent in the Realizeit system?

2.2 Dataset

For this study, we used the data from the first two student cohorts of the programme, cohorts 2016 and 2017 that was available in the first quarter of 2018. Cohort 2016 contains 29 students and have started their industry placements. Cohort 2017 contains 26 students who are in the initial phase of their programme. Some of the topics at CSU contain several sub learning activities for which data is logged, others only contain an assignment to wrap the topic up at the end. In this exploration we therefore only consider data at the level of the topics, not on the level of sub learning activities.

2.3 Approach

As this concerns exploratory research, in an iterative process we started out with raw data from the system and tried to combine data and structure data in such a way it would present different kinds of behaviour related to the topic tree. We ran analyses using these metrics and find out if we could somehow describe this in terms of effective study behaviour. The team of researchers consisted of a data scientist, an learning analytics researcher and two engineering education researchers who teach at CSU, so different ideas and frameworks informed the decisions. In this paper, we present some of the strongest metrics regarding ease of interpretation and their predictive value.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Order of the activities and time between them

The first question to be addressed is how far do students move with the topic tree on consecutive learning activities? In Figure 2(a) a histogram of the distance between topics is plotted for all students. We can see that by far, the most common distance is zero. This means that after a student completes a topic, the most common next thing for them to do is another topic within the same branch. Students tend to see the series of related topics through until they have done everything within that neighbourhood.

We can see that the distribution is positively skewed meaning that students tend to stay local. However, there are some large distances between consecutive learning activities on topics with some that are 10 to 30 connections apart. Some large jumps are inevitable given the shape of the topic tree; students who finish out a branch will be required to make a large jump across the tree to commence a new branch.

Figure 2(b) shows the time in days between consecutive topics. In this figure the bar at position 31 represents all time gaps of 31 days or more. Again, we can see the distribution is positively skewed meaning that students typically do not leave much time between learning activities. In fact, the most common time between topics is zero days meaning that students attempt multiple topics on any days that they are active. This suggests that students allocate time to go through a number of topics on a single day. From the perspective of study behaviour this is an effective strategy as it allows students to spend as much time on a topic as they feel they need to learn to master it. In regular programmes students often complain about the fragmentation of their time to sit down and work on difficult topics, as by their programme they are required to participate in multiple educational activities on a given day.

Figure 2: Frequency of distance (a) and time in days (b) between topics.

These two insights, students stay local and complete multiple topics on that same day are further highlighted by Figure 3. The joint distribution of the two-previous metrics is plotted with frequency on a log scale. The peak of the distribution is clearly at (0,0) and represents 38% of all activities. This is nearly an order of magnitude larger than the next largest distance-time combination and suggests that some level of bingeing on topics is taking place.

Figure 3: A heatmap showing the joint frequency distribution of distance and time in days between topics. Frequency is plotted on a log scale.

One interesting subset of consecutive learning activities to examine is the next activity directly after they complete a topic. In other words, when a student completes a topic, what is the next thing they do? How far away do they move on the topic tree? As suggested by the above analysis students tend to stay local and attempt the next learning activity on the same day. It has been observed that this seems like a Netflix effect, where students ‘binge’ on topics on the same branch before they do anything else [3].

3.2 Activity after completions

From 3.1 it shows how all students binge to a certain extent, however, there are two interesting, and in some ways opposite, subsets of students that are worth pointing out that were identified based on visual inspection of the data. Both subsets are displayed in Figure 4, where Cohort 2016 students are shown in red and Cohort 2017 students are shown in blue. The numbers in each graph represent a single student. Figure 4 shows a selection of students who show the pattern in behaviour.

For the first subset, shown in Figure 4(a), the distribution of their distances to the next topic after completing a topic is positively skewed, meaning they stay local. This is in line with what we have seen before. However, with a peak at zero, this means that after they complete a topic, the most common next activity for them to do is to revise that topic. In a sense these students are bingers, as they stay local, but they revise topics before they move on. These students are revisers.

The second subset, shown in Figure 4(b), generally have the same shaped positively skewed distribution. What is notable about these students is that, while they generally stay local, they have no consecutive activities with a distance of zero after completing a topic. This means that they never go directly back into a topic after completing it, they always attempt a lesson on a new topic. They may, however, revise the topic at a later date. These students may still binge, but they also jump.

Figure 4: Distance to the next topic after completing a topic for two subsets of students (a) who revise a topic upon completion straight away and (b) students do not.

In general we discern between three major patterns of behaviour that overlap to some extent:

- Bingers – these are students who stay on the same branch in the topic tree and do all topics within a certain branch within a certain time.
- Jumpers – these are students who go through the topic tree seemingly random. They finish a single topic, tend not to revise the topic and tend not to see through all topics within a single branch. There may also be more time between the topics these students engage in.
- Revisers – these are students who will go back to revise a topic as soon as they finish it.

As these behaviours overlap to some extent, it is hard to discern clearly delineated groups based on it.

4 CONCLUSIONS AND DISCUSSION

Lindsey and Morgan [3] observed that students move through the topic tree in a similar way as many people watch series on Netflix: they tend to stay within in the same series and watch all episodes of a series in a short amount of time. Some students revise: the first thing they do when they finish a topic is to start all over again with the same topic. Some students do not revise right away, but they move to the next topic which may be the next topic on the branch but does not have to be. Bingeing seems like an

effective strategy to study, as it would help the students to spend a considerable amount of time on task and to stay focused. Revision and self-testing are well established and effective study behaviours. Jumpers do not revise right away and do not always come back to all topics. These observations fit in well with Carroll's model for school learning: some students need to spend more time on a topic to master it than others and some students have more effective study behaviours than others. From the data we studied it is not possible to make any claims on how the students spent their time exactly and how much time they spent on their studies of the topics, but we are able to discern a number of behaviours that seem striking based on the data. Although these findings may not seem significant, we believe they are: in these innovative learning environments we do not know how students deal with the materials, how they move through the curriculum. In regular education we have a good grasp of principles of design to support student success. In this innovative curriculum it is up to the students to make decisions regarding their study behaviour, but it is still important to understand student behaviour to monitor the effectiveness of the environment, but also to be able to spot students who may be at risk and think of interventions that are appropriate in this unique context.

Next steps in this endeavour are to explore the dimensions that are underlying for this behaviour, to create a link with student performance, but also to start a dialogue with the students about these study behaviours: what motivates them to study in this way, what do they feel they gain through these behaviours and how does that tie in with their other educational activities in the curriculum? We intend to pursue these questions further in future research.

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